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Research Article

CORRELATION OF PSA IMMUNOSTAIN WITH GLEASON'S GRADING AND SCORING SYSTEM OF PROSTATIC CARCINOMA

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Abstract:

Background: Prostatic carcinoma is the commonest malignancy in males above the age of sixty-five years. Prognosis of prostatic carcinoma depends on clinical status and grade of tumor. Gleason scoring system for tumor differentiation is more superior to other systems. The prostate cancer clinical sequence is flexible and at cannot adequately be identified by histological procedures only. Introducing of immuno-stains to the study of prostatic carcinoma has so long as an additional sub-classification of prostatic carcinoma, appreciation of definite cell varieties and dissimilar categories of carcinoma prostate.

Objective: To assess immune histochemical staining of tissue prostate specific antigen in prostatic carcinoma using Gleason's grading and scoring system.

Material and Methods: It is a descriptive cross-sectional study conducted at Sheikh Zayed Hospital, Lahore for 6 months. Ninety cases of prostatic adenocarcinoma were collected from the Department of Urology and General Surgery, in order to assess tissue prostate specific antigen expression on prostatic adenocarcinoma and its correlation with the Gleason's grading and scoring System. Ninety biopsies of prostate CA with the histological diagnosis of adenocarcinoma were included.

Results: The mean age of patient was 66.40 ± 5.78 years. Gleason's score 3 was noted in 5 (5.6%) cases, score 4 in 24 (26.7%) cases, score 5 in 1 (1.1%) cases, score 6 in 24 (26.7%) cases, score 7 in 6 (6.7%) cases, score 8 in 17 (18.9%) cases, score 9 in 5 (5.6%) cases and score 10 in 8 (8.9%) cases. Staining intensity was 0 in 6 cases, (+) in 19 cases, ++ in 37 cases and +++ in 28 cases. Staining intensity showed strong association between tumor differentiation ($p < 0.05$). Similarly, Gleason score showed strong association with staining intensity ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: In conclusion, the study shows correlation of PSA immune stain with Gleason's grading and scoring system of prostate carcinoma showing good correlation.

Key Words: Prostate cancer, adenocarcinoma, PSA, Gleason score.

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INTRODUCTION:

Carcinoma of Prostatic is the communal malignancy in males over the age of 65 years. In the countries of European Union, thirteen percent of malignancies investigated in men reveal prostatic carcinoma.¹ Recent advancement in surgical and diagnostic procedures resulted significantly in improved outcome. Most common histological type of carcinoma prostate is adenocarcinoma developing in acini of prostatic ducts comprising 95-98% of all prostate cancers. Other rare types are small cell carcinoma, mucinous carcinoma, signet ring cell carcinoma, adenoid cystic carcinoma, and neuroendocrine variety.² Among the non-carcinomatous types include primary prostatic lymphoma, rhabdomyosarcoma and leiomyomas. Prostate carcinoma are mostly multifocal out of which 70% are found in peripheral zone and 20% are situated in transitional zone.^{3,4}

Architectural disturbance, anaplasia and invasion are important histological criteria for diagnosing carcinoma of prostate. Low Gleason score (< 5) carcinoma of prostate usually have less violent behavior and high Gleason score (8-10) carcinoma prostate are usually extremely aggressive. The less differentiated tumor can cause lower PSA (Prostate Specific Antigen) concentration as compared to well differentiated. To diagnose the prostatic carcinoma a gold standard triad includes Digital Rectal Inspection, PSA levels and Trans Rectal Ultrasonography. Prognosis of prostatic carcinoma be influenced by tumor ranking and clinical eminence. Gleason scoring system for tumor differentiation is more superior to other systems. The Gleason's categorizing system is grounded on gland architecture, grade of glandular diversity and stromal annexation but does not relay on gradation of nuclear anaplasia.⁷ PSA immunohistochemical stain is most commonly used marker for malignant cells of prostatic origin. It is a 33KD glycoprotein with serine protease activity.⁸

Monoclonal anti PSA antibody found to be beneficial in minor gland propagations in which the variance judgement comprises seminal vesicle. Polyclonal anti PSA antibody is considered superior for poorly differentiated neoplasms. Positive cells percentage in prostatic carcinoma and concentration of immunostaining diminished increasingly with aggregate tumor grade, especially through monoclonal anti PSA. Literature review has shown Polyclonal anti PSA is highly profound than the monoclonal antibody in the of prostatic carcinoma diagnosis.⁹ It is found that staining of PSA deteriorated from benign epithelium to prostatic adenocarcinoma and PIN suggestive of regulated contrarily and lessened in growth and malignant conversion. The poor prognosis is due to lymphatic spread and it may be the initial signal to

look as if in some patients without earlier outcome of prostate adenocarcinoma.¹⁰ In prostate cancer patients serum PSA levels upsurges equitably with tumor measurements as well as grade of differentiation. A study has reported increased serum levels by 3.5ng/ml for every cm of prostate carcinoma a level at least 10 times higher than in BPH.⁶

A study conducted in Nagasaki University, School Medicine, revealed that 75 and 56 of 79 specimens were positive for PSA protein (94.9%) and positive for PSA Mrna (70.9%) respectively. ⁶Unwell distinguished prostatic adenocarcinoma show PSA staining even though it possibly be focal. PSA has in over-all been extra sensitive. 15% has shown completely negative stain for PSA. ¹¹Clinical development of prostate cancer is very inconstant and at times cannot reasonably be detected by histological approaches only. Introducing immune stains to study of prostatic carcinoma has providing a further sub-grading of prostatic carcinoma, appreciation of certain cell kinds and diverse categories of carcinoma prostate. Higher scoring malignancy is associated to lower PSA appearance of tissue and it represents damage of function by less production of secretory proteins which is related to nuclear/DNA abnormalities. These mutations cause the production of clones of cells more dedifferentiated from original status with more chance of metastasis and poorer outcome to survival.

OBJECTIVE

To evaluate immunohistochemical staining of tissue prostate specific antigen in prostatic carcinoma using Gleason's grading and scoring system.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study design: Cross sectional study

Venue: Histopathology department, Sheikh Zayed hospital Lahore

Duration: 6 months.

Sample size: 90 patients

Sampling technique: Non-probability, consecutive sampling

Selection criteria:

Inclusion Criteria: 90 biopsies of prostate CA were included:

- Only those biopsy specimen which were received in 10% formalin
- Prostatic biopsy with the histological diagnosis of adenocarcinoma prostate
- Cases with well-preserved morphology in hematoxylin and eosin sections.

Exclusion criteria

1. Poorly preserved specimens and sections
2. Benign prostate lesions.
3. All other malignancies (local and metastatic) except adenocarcinoma prostate.

Clinical Data: The significant clinical data was obtained from the patients and the hospital record and all the information was recorded in the proforma as annexure.

Source of Specimen/ Nature of Biopsy: The entire specimen were obtained from the prostate and included:

1. Transurethral resections of prostate. (TURP)
2. Prostatectomies
3. Needle biopsies

GRADING OF TUMOR: Gleason's scoring criteria performed according to grading chart provided:¹²

Grade 1: Simple round glands, closely packed in rounded masses with well-defined edges

Grade 2: Simple rounded glands, loosely packed, in vague rounded masses with loosely defined edges

Grade 3a: Medium sized single glands of irregular shape and irregular spacing with ill-defined infiltrating edges.

Grade 3b: 3a + every small glands which must not from single chain or cords.

Grade 3c: Papillary and cribriform epithelium in smooth rounded cylindrical and masses no necrosis

Grade 4a: Small medium or large glands fused into cords chains or ragged infiltrating masses.

Grade 4b: Similar to 4a, but many large clear cells sometimes resembling hypernephroma.

Grade 5a: Papillary and cribriform epithelium in smooth round to masses, more solid than 3b and with central necrosis.

Grade 5b: Anaplastic adenocarcinoma in ragged sheets.

GLEASON'S SCORING SYSTEMS

Gleason's Score is grouped into 3 categories:

- 2-4 (Well Differentiated)
- 5-7 (Moderately differentiated)
- 8-10 (Poorly Differentiated)

This grouping was performed to simplify the data, to corresponds to well, moderate and poor Differentiation, although this grouping is not universally used.

Intensity of Staining: The staining intensity of tumor cells was graded by comparing with benign

epithelial cells on the same slide. 4 points semi-quantitative criteria were used.

+++ Strong staining with all epithelial cells in a malignant acinus + staining bright red brown will be considered as score 3 (Subjective observation).

++ Moderate staining with >50% epithelial cells in a malignant acinus staining well to moderate or all epithelial cells in a malignant acinus staining weakly will score 2.

+ Weak staining with <50% epithelial cells in a malignant acinus staining weakly will be score 1.

0 No staining will be score 0.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 20 was used for data analysis.

RESULTS:

A total of 90 cases were included in the study. The mean age of patients was 66.40±5.78 years with most of the patients in the age range 61-70 years. In the sample, 30 (33.3%) patients had well differentiated tumor, 30 (33.3%) patients had moderately differentiated tumor and 30 (33.3%) patients had poorly differentiated tumor. Table 1

Gleason's score 3 was noted in 5 (5.6%) cases, score 4 in 24 (26.7%) cases, score 5 in 1 (1.1%) cases, score 6 in 24 (26.7%) cases, score 7 in 6 (6.7%) cases, score 8 in 17 (18.9%) cases, score 9 in 5 (5.6%) cases and score 10 in 8 (8.9%) cases. Table 2

Staining intensity was 0 in 6 cases, (+) in 19 cases, ++ in 37 cases and +++ in 28 cases. Staining intensity 0 showed poor differentiation of tumor in all cases, staining (+) showed poor differentiation in all cases, staining ++ showed 10 well differentiated, 22 moderately differentiated and 5 poorly differentiated tumor. Staining +++ showed 20 well differentiated, 8 moderately differentiated and no poorly differentiated tumor. The value of $p < 0.05$ showed the strong association between tumor differentiation with staining intensity. Similarly, Gleason score 10 was present in all staining 0 cases. Distribution of Gleason score for tumor staining in given in Table 3. The value of $p < 0.05$ showed strong association between Gleason's score with staining intensity.

Table No. 1: Characteristics of patients

N	90
Mean age	66.40±5.78
45-50years	12 (13.3%)
51-60years	18 (20%)
61-70years	32 (35.6%)
71-80years	28 (31.1%)
Tumor differentiation	
Well differentiated	30 (33.3%)
Moderate differentiated	30 (33.3%)
Poo differentiated	30 (33.3%)

Table no 2: Showing Percentage Cellularity & Frequency of Tumor

Gleason score	Frequency	Percentage
3	5	5.6%
4	24	26.7%
5	1	1.1%
6	24	26.7%
7	6	6.7%
8	17	18.9%
9	5	5.6%
10	8	8.9%

Table no 3: Comparison of Tumor differentiation and Gleason score with staining intensity

Tumor differentiation	Staining intensity				Total
	0 (n=6)	+	++	+++	
Well differentiated	0	0	10	20	30
Moderate differentiated	0	0	22	8	30
Poorly differentiated	6	19	5	0	30
Gleason's score					
3	0	0	0	4	4
4	0	0	10	15	25
5	0	0	0	1	1
6	0	0	15	8	23
7	0	0	7	0	7
8	0	13	4	0	17
9	0	4	1	0	5
10	6	2	0	0	8

DISCUSSION:

The most common pathologies affecting prostate are: inflammation, hyperplasia, adenosis, pre-malignancies and adenocarcinoma.¹³ Unlike most cancers which have peak age of incidence, the incidence and prevalence of prostate carcinoma continue to increase with advancing age after 50 years of age, both incidence rate and mortality increase almost exponentially 95% of prostate

carcinoma are diagnosed between the age of 45-90 years with a median age of 72 years.¹⁴

In this study the mean age of patients whose samples were taken was 66.40±5.78 years. This study also concluded 33.3% were well differentiated, 33.3% moderately differentiated and 33.3% were labeled as poorly differentiated tumors. A study done in Jinnah Post graduate medical institute showed that most of the prostatic tumors are more common in age group between 60-70 years. This study also concluded 32% were well distinguished, 56% moderately distinguished and 12% were labelled as poorly differentiated tumors. Various risk factors have a role in disease occurrence such as age, race, hormonal factors and environmental factors.³

Catalona et al., the histological findings indicated that their patients had more aggressive disease than patients in our region. In their study, 60% of patients showed cancer of high histological grade (Gleason's score 8-10) compared to 13.55% in our patients, and there were no patients with low grade (Gleason's score 2-adenocarcinoma in their series). In our study the Gleason score of most of the patients 26% are 4 & 6.¹⁵ A weakness of the Gleason system is that it has a pronounced clustering in the mid-range of the scores. Some reports of radical prostatectomy series observed as many as 86-89% of the tumors presenting a Gleason score 6 or 7.^{16, 17} Gleason pattern 1 is extremely rare. None of the patients in this study had a Gleason score of 1. Pattern 2 is usually mixed with some pattern 3 resulting in a Gleason score 5. As a result, Gleason score 2, 3, and 4 are only exceptionally assigned and it is recommended not to use scores 2-4 on needle biopsies.¹⁸

Recent overall survival rates for GS 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10 have been reported as 51%, 45%, 34%, 25%, and 15%, respectively with significant survival differences between GS7 and GS8. However, no survival differences were observed between GS3+4 versus 4+3.¹⁹ Compared to disease-specific mortality, a study of the 10-year prostate cancer-specific survival rates found no difference in disease-specific mortality between GS4+3 and GS8-10 prostate cancers, and patients with GS4+3 disease were at an increased risk for prostate cancer-specific mortality compared to those with GS3+4. The 10-year prostate cancer-specific survival rate for GS $\leq$ 6, 3+4, 4+3, and GS $\geq$ 8 was found to be 98.4%, 92.1%, 76.5%, and 69.9%, respectively.²⁰

Limitations of Gleason grading system

Although current revisions have improved the Gleason grading system, it continues to have limitations. Recent modifications have made the Gleason grading system much more complex. This complexity can be confusing for patients and clinicians. Gleason score 6 is now recommended as the lowest grade to be assigned on prostate biopsy. Patients may assume that a diagnosis of Gleason score 6 on biopsy means their tumor is in the mid-range of aggressiveness rather than having the best prognosis. In addition, many former Gleason score 6 tumors are now reclassified as Gleason score 7 in the modified system. Modern Gleason score 6 tumors have a much better prognosis than reported in the older literature.

CONCLUSION:

Gleason score continues to be the single most powerful predictor of prostate cancer prognosis and plays a significant role in clinical management. The correct diagnosis and grading of prostate cancer is

crucial for a patient's prognosis and therapeutic options. The ISUP grading consensus conferences held in 2005 and then in 2014 have improved the overall grading system. However, this system also has limitations which a new prostatic grading system can improve in future. While Gleason score is statistically significant with staining intensity, age of patients, tumor differentiation and cellularity at 5% level of significance. Similarly, Staining intensity, age of patients, tumor differentiation and cellularity percentage has pairwise positive association and the p-value $< \alpha = 5\%$. It shows that all the results are pairwise statistically significant.

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